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Title:	A Genealogy of Gestures: On the nature and emergence of forms of gestural communication within shared routines
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42 **A Genealogy of Gestures: On the nature and emergence of forms of gestural**
 43 **communication within shared routines**
 44

45 “Communication is the origin of the mind” (Kaye, 1982, p. 4)
 46

47 “A speck of behavior, a fleck of culture, and—voilà!—a gesture” (Geertz, 1973, p. 6).
 48

49 Communication is interwoven with many aspects of human development, from
 50 cognitive to social cognitive development. Thus, in order to understand how mind
 51 emerges from nature, we have to understand human communicative development.
 52 Although it might be assumed that language is the proto-typical form of human
 53 communication, even before children begin to talk, they are already intentionally
 54 communicating with gestures. Thus, it behooves us to examine how these early forms of
 55 communication develop because this allows for observing the emergence of forms of
 56 relations on which communication is based, before we become mesmerized by the
 57 complexity of language. In order to study gestures, as Geertz (1973, p. 6) beautifully
 58 articulated, we must pay attention to the social context— “a fleck of culture”— that
 59 makes it possible to get from “a speck of behavior” to an intentionally communicative
 60 gesture.

61 Grappling with explaining the development of gestures requires examining
 62 conceptions of communication, which rest on assumptions about how knowledge
 63 develops and how meaning is conveyed. In considering the presuppositions underlying
 64 theories of communicative development, two families can be distinguished. One begins
 65 with mind in explaining relations, but therefore does not explain the origin of the mind,
 66 whereas the other begins with relations as primary and central in explaining the
 67 development of human forms of cognition. From this relational perspective “gesture and
 68 communication come before mind and self” (Jopling, 1993, p. 526). This approach
 69 explains human rationality and communication as emerging through conduct and
 70 interaction, which contrasts with assuming that the beginning point in human
 71 development is individual cognition (Bernstein, 2010; Jopling, 1993; Mead, 1934).
 72

73 In the context of theories of gestural development, one approach is based on a
 74 cognitivist worldview (Camaioni et al., 2004; Tomasello et al., 2005; Tomasello et al.,
 75 2007). According to this approach, mind is presupposed, which is private and separate
 76 from and underlies behavior, understood as an expression of underlying mental processes.
 77 From this it follows that children begin to communicate intentionally only after they
 78 understand that others are intentional agents with attention that can be directed. This
 79 insight develops through a process of simulation, and by the time infants start using
 80 gestures, it is assumed that they have a fair grasp of social relations, so the research focus
 81 is on analyzing what communicative intentions children are trying to convey when they
 82 gesture (Tomasello et al., 2005; Tomasello et al., 2007). Interaction and shared
 83 background with others would facilitate this process but does not constitute this
 84 development (Carpendale, 2018; Carpendale et al., 2013, 2021).
 85

84 Alternatively, from a process-relational worldview that we endorse, meaning is
 85 not in the child’s mind or attached to elements in the environment. Meaning is co-created

86 in shared activities, in relations with others and objects, which in turn are rooted in
 87 human forms of life (Canfield, 1995; 2007; Carpendale et al., 2013; Carpendale et al.,
 88 2021; Wittgenstein, 1953/2009). It is through this action that is embedded in meaningful
 89 interactions, that intention, communication, and thinking can be progressively built.
 90 Therefore, gestures are not initially based on an underlying understanding of social
 91 relations; rather, they develop within shared practices. In this sense, our aim is to
 92 investigate how communication develops within shared activities between adults and
 93 infants, focusing not only on fully mastered gestures but also on transitional events in the
 94 emergence of gestures between infants' instrumental actions and their intentional
 95 gestures.

96 In the study of children's early gestures, the primary focus of research attention
 97 has been on pointing gestures, perhaps because this gesture appears to be ubiquitous in
 98 infant development and can be used to convey many meanings (e.g., Carpendale &
 99 Lewis, 2021). This gesture has been of interest for some time (e.g., Carpendale &
 100 Carpendale, 2010; Shinn, 1900; Tomasello et al., 2007). However, less attention has been
 101 paid to the development of other forms of gestures, such as conventional and symbolic
 102 gestures (Acredolo & Goodwyn, 1985, 1988; Goldin-Meadow & Feldman, 1977). We
 103 examine the "genealogy of gestures" because we are concerned with the origins and
 104 development of various forms of gestures, and how they differ and are interrelated in the
 105 process of development (see Wittgenstein, 1980b, §722, on a genealogy of psychological
 106 concepts). We suggest that it may be informative for our understanding of meaning and
 107 communication to examine the development of various gestures that have so far been
 108 relatively neglected such as conventional and symbolic gestures. From our perspective,
 109 these forms of gestures must be based on the same general processes through which
 110 communication develops, but they might differ in their developmental pathway. We
 111 propose that it may be useful to categorize the diversity of early gestures into three broad
 112 (but not completely distinct) families, based on somewhat different underlying processes
 113 of development: 1) gestures based on infants' spontaneous actions that others respond to,
 114 allowing infants to learn the meaning their actions have for others (e.g., the "arms up
 115 gesture" and reaching gestures); 2) conventional gestures that are culturally specific, and
 116 must involve, to some degree, imitation of a physical movement (e.g., waving and
 117 clapping); and 3) symbolic gestures in which an action is understood as referring to
 118 another action, object, or event, such as using a twisting motion to refer to taking the lid
 119 off a jar (e.g., Goldin-Meadow & Feldman, 1977). Although these three forms of gestures
 120 differ, we argue that they rely on the same processes through which meaning is conveyed.
 121 Thus, it is important to examine assumptions about the process through which
 122 communication works, that is, assumptions regarding the nature of meaning.

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Views of Meaning and Communication

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Gestural communication is the earliest form of intentional human communication.
 Therefore, an analysis of the development of gestures will necessarily be based on
 assumptions about the nature of communication and how meaning is conveyed. This
 makes it necessary to explicate the underlying assumptions about communication on
 which researchers base their theories, methodologies, and interpretation of results. A
 common philosophical assumption regarding the nature of meaning is that it can be

131 attached to representations such as words or utterances (Goldberg, 1991; McDonough,
 132 1989). This leads to the code model of language, according to which language functions
 133 by transmitting meaning from one individual to another. Meaning, according to this view,
 134 is attached to words and messages transmitted to others, which are then decoded to
 135 retrieve the meaning of the message (Canfield, 1995, 2007). It is with a critique of this
 136 view of meaning that Wittgenstein begins his *Philosophical Investigations* (1953/2009).
 137 As an example of this way of thinking regarding the nature of meaning, Wittgenstein
 138 draws on a passage in Saint Augustine's *Confessions* in which Augustine imagines
 139 himself as an infant trying to communicate to adults that he is hungry, and he learns the
 140 language used by adults around him. For Wittgenstein, this gives

141 "a particular picture of the essence of human language. It is this: the words in
 142 language name objects—sentences are combinations of such names.—In this
 143 picture of language we find the roots of the following idea: Every word has a
 144 meaning. This meaning is correlated with the world. It is the object for which the
 145 word stands." (Wittgenstein, 1953/2009, §1)

146
 147 This presupposition regarding meaning as a naming game has not become
 148 outdated in the 1500 years since Saint Augustine wrote his *Confessions* (Wills, 2001). It is
 149 still widely accepted and can be found, for example, in Pinker's (1994) and Chomsky's
 150 (2007) approaches to language. Chomsky claimed that children are born with all possible
 151 word meanings (e.g., Chomsky, 2007). This foundational presupposition presupposes the
 152 view of meaning that Wittgenstein critiqued.

153 Although Augustine does not refer to different types of words, he appears to be
 154 primarily thinking of nouns referring to objects. Wittgenstein suggests that this
 155 "philosophical notion of meaning is at home in a primitive idea of the way language
 156 functions. But one might instead say that it is the idea of a language more primitive than
 157 ours" (Wittgenstein, 1953/2009, §2). To consider this possibility, Wittgenstein imagines a
 158 language that would fit with the description given by Augustine. It is a language that
 159 would enable communication between a builder and an assistant, through the use of
 160 words that stand for building stones such as block, pillar, and slab. The builder could then
 161 call out the words and the assistant would bring the correct stones. Perhaps Augustine
 162 does describe a system of communication that accounts for this situation, and this shared
 163 practice of fetching named objects is something that some dogs can learn, particularly
 164 border collies. However, it clearly does not include everything we call language
 165 (Wittgenstein, 1953/2009, §3). Wittgenstein refers to this whole process "consisting of
 166 language and the actions into which it is woven, the 'language game'" (Wittgenstein,
 167 1953/2009, §7). Calling out words such as "block" and receiving an object in return
 168 would be one example of a language-game.

169 Wittgenstein then suggests that it is possible to imagine an extension of the first
 170 language-game by adding numbers up to five. Now the builder can ask the assistant to
 171 report the number of slabs or blocks remaining. For example, "Such a report or statement
 172 might run: 'Five slabs'" (Wittgenstein, 1953/2009, §21). But now a problem arises for the
 173 view of meaning as being attached to words or utterances because, "what is the difference
 174 between the report or statement 'Five slabs' and the order 'Five slabs!'" (Wittgenstein,
 175 1953/2009, §21). Although these utterances could be stated with different expressions and

176 tone of voice, it is also possible that they might not differ in this way. So how is it that the
 177 same utterance can convey two different meanings? This is a flawed view of meaning
 178 because it cannot account for how it is possible to understand which meaning is intended.
 179 In this imagined primitive language, we have considered only two meanings based on two
 180 forms of interaction—ordering and reporting—but the more general point is that any
 181 utterance or representation can convey multiple meanings. This aspect of communication
 182 cannot be explained by the view of language as a naming game according to which
 183 meaning is attached to words or utterances (like attaching a label to something) and
 184 transmitted to others who decode the message.

185 Wittgenstein considers many additional language-games added onto the initial
 186 primitive activity, but even the two considered here illustrate the difficulty faced by the
 187 view of language assumed by Augustine, as well as contemporary researchers. Instead,
 188 Wittgenstein suggests a different view of language as based on activities. From this
 189 perspective, the two identical utterances can convey different meanings in the context of
 190 different patterns of interaction between the builder and the assistant—different language-
 191 games. And Wittgenstein emphasizes that “Here the term ‘*language-game*’ is meant to
 192 bring into prominence the fact that the *speaking* of language is part of an activity, or of a
 193 form of life” (Wittgenstein, 1953/2009, §23, italics in original).

194 For Wittgenstein, meaning is based on shared social routines, or “steady ways of
 195 living, regular ways of acting” (Wittgenstein, 1976, p. 420). Instead of locating the source
 196 of meaning in the individual’s brain, Wittgenstein located it in one’s cultural world,
 197 beginning within everyday lived practical interactions. He quoted Goethe in stating that
 198 “[l]anguage, I want to say, is a refinement, ‘In the beginning was the deed’”
 199 (Wittgenstein, 1980a, p. 31). This is “Wittgenstein’s Copernican revolution in the theory
 200 of meaning” (McDonough, 1989, p. 19), in which he makes the move from viewing
 201 meaning as located in the individual to locating the source of meaning in our relations
 202 with others. In Peter Winch’s (1958, p. 123) words, “... our language and our social
 203 relations are just two different sides of the same coin. To give an account of the meaning
 204 of a word is to describe how a word is used; and to describe how it is used is to describe
 205 the social intercourse into which it enters.” Thus, “to imagine a language means to image
 206 a form of life” (Wittgenstein, 1953/2009, §19). In the process of learning a language, the
 207 child learns to master the “customs, or patterns of interaction, within which words
 208 function” (Canfield, 1999, p. 158). Drawing on this conception of meaning we now turn
 209 to applying it to understanding gestural development.

210

211 **A Relational Approach to Gesture Development**

212 We have reviewed arguments that meaning is not fixed to gestures, words,
 213 utterances, or any representation, but that, instead, meaning depends on being “embedded
 214 into the flow of characteristic patterns of human behavior” (Goldberg, 1991, p. 62). This
 215 means that “if the life surrounding a remark were quite different from what it is, ... then
 216 the remark would not have the meaning it does” (Goldberg, 1991, p. 62). As an empirical
 217 illustration of this position, consider an experiment on the topic of young children’s
 218 understanding of pointing. Fourteen- to 18-month-old infants worked on putting together
 219 a puzzle with one experimenter, and with another experimenter they cleaned up the room.
 220 Later, when the “puzzle experimenter” pointed to a piece of the puzzle, infants tried to

221 put it in the puzzle, but when the “clean-up experimenter” made the exact same gesture of
 222 pointing to the puzzle piece, infants understood it as a request to clean it up and put the
 223 piece away. These infants understood the same gesture differently depending on the
 224 experience they had shared with that individual (Liebal et al., 2009).

225 This view of meaning as based on shared ways of interacting was also
 226 presupposed in George Herbert Mead’s (1934) approach to meaning. He argued that
 227 meaning is already there in the social act even before infants become aware that they are
 228 communicating. Thus, he also roots meaning in shared human activities. Taking a
 229 Meadian approach, Clark (1978, p. 252) argues that “A gesture is distilled from a
 230 preexisting social activity involving two organisms behaving in the physical world, and as
 231 such it comes into existence already equipped with its own ‘meaning’”. Thus, children do
 232 not acquire gestures as instruments to express their inner meanings or intentions (Clark,
 233 1978). Instead, gestures are co-constructed by the child and the adult acting in shared
 234 activities and interpreting the other’s behaviors as meaningful.

235 Based on this view of meaning we can now turn to applying this way of thinking
 236 to understanding forms of gestures and their development. We present a processrelational
 237 approach, which we argue provides a coherent foundation for the investigation of how
 238 infants learn to communicate with gestures. The study of gestures provides a way to
 239 document the emergence of communication because it is possible to observe infants
 240 learning to master important social routines as they acquire communicative skills. The
 241 goal of the process-relational approach we endorse is to describe and explain how infants
 242 learn to convey meaning with gestures, and later words, through participating in shared
 243 routine activities with their caregivers. Process-relational, activity-based explanations
 244 provide detailed descriptions of the increasingly complex shared activities that infants are
 245 immersed in from birth, as well as how infants’ emerging physical and social skills
 246 develop and converge to result in increasingly complex forms of social understanding.

247

248

Three Families of Gestures

249 The three families of gestures that we present group together gestures that seem to
 250 develop through similar interactive and social processes. In discussing forms of gesture,
 251 we are not referring to the social functions of the gestures, such as imperatives or
 252 declaratives, because, as we will show, most types of gestures can be used to perform
 253 multiple social acts. Instead, we suggest a categorization based on the developmental
 254 origins of gestures, that allows us to focus not only on gestures as isolated behaviors but
 255 on the interactions leading to their development. In these interactions, it becomes clear
 256 that, in addition to analyzing matured and conventional gestures, considering transitional
 257 forms of gestures (between actions and gestures) and how they progressively acquire
 258 complexity, flexibility, and conventionality is essential for understanding the gesture’s
 259 origin and how meaning is co-constructed. We will use examples of observations from
 260 diary studies to illustrate these various forms of gestures.

261

262

1) Gestures originating in infants’ spontaneous actions

263

264

265

During their first year of life, before learning to communicate intentionally,
 infants are first involved in routine everyday activities that they become familiar with
 (e.g., feeding, object exchange, book reading). It is in these shared activities that children

266 learn that their actions have specific meanings to others, begin to anticipate parents'
267 responses, and look for ways to actively participate and even elicit these patterns of
268 interactions, usually through gestures. Children's ability to engage in these forms of
269 interaction is not based on underlying insights about others as intentional agents, but on
270 these shared practices in which children progressively have more active roles as their
271 social understanding and skills increase. This process through which intentional
272 communication begins is rooted in patterns of interaction that gradually become more
273 complex (Carpendale & Lewis, 2021).

274 One example of these patterns of interaction is the development of the arms-up
275 gesture. Authors have described that the arms-up gestures originate in early routines of
276 caregivers picking their infants up, and infants enjoying the comfort of their caregivers
277 while being held. This is considered a typical human form of interaction between infants
278 and caregivers that originates from the child being born in a helpless situation
279 (Carpendale & Lewis, 2021). As infants become familiar with the "picking-up routine"
280 (Lock, 1978), they begin to participate in it more actively. First, infants adjust and stiffen
281 their bodies when their caregivers reach to them (Reddy et al., 2013). Later, they show
282 anticipation of the routine by raising their arms in response to their caregivers reaching to
283 pick them up (Lock, 1978, 1992; Reddy et al., 2013). Gradually, likely motivated by their
284 desire for comfort, and learning that being picked up is an enjoyable activity, infants will
285 begin to raise their arms before the caregiver initiates this routine. Infants are now
286 initiating a routine and at this point we consider it to be an intentional gesture. However,
287 it is important to note that the arms-up gesture likely would not become a gesture without
288 shared knowledge of the "picking-up routine" (Lock, 1978; Edwards, 1978). It cannot
289 originate in other arm-extending actions because this gesture involves extending both
290 arms rather than reaching with one arm as infants do when reaching for objects.

291 This is only one of the typical ways in which meaning is co-constructed during
292 early parent-child interactions. Other ways of early interaction emerge, not by the child
293 responding to an adult's action or by learning a social routine, but by the child orienting
294 within and spontaneously acting within a social world. Infants' interests and desires are
295 expressed in their natural reactions from early in development (e.g., reaching and leaning
296 towards interesting objects, raising arms towards approaching adults, and crying when
297 hungry). From the first months of life, the infant spontaneously acts on the world with
298 instrumental objectives, without initially intending to communicate (e.g., trying to grasp a
299 nearby object). As these behaviors are manifest and visible, adults may interpret the
300 child's actions as meaningful according to the context and respond to them as if the
301 actions were communicative. In this way, parents introduce their children to triadic
302 communicative interactions before children are able to do it by themselves. Through these
303 repeated interactions, infants become progressively aware of how others respond to their
304 actions and begin to anticipate them, resulting in having a more active role in infantadult
305 interactions in specific contexts. Eventually, the infant begins to use the action in a
306 communicatively intentional way.

307 Let us now consider some examples of how this process takes place in everyday
308 interactions for different forms of gestures:

309

310 **From grasping and reaching actions to requesting gestures.** Extending the arm
 311 to make requests may develop from the infant reaching for objects with one arm and the
 312 parent responding to this by giving the object because the infant's desire is clearly
 313 manifest in her action. This repeated interaction allows the child to anticipate the parent's
 314 response to her action. As transitional behaviors, previous research has observed that
 315 children begin to reach more frequently in the presence of others, but do not show other
 316 signs of expecting a response (Ramenzoni & Liszkowski, 2016). Eventually, the child
 317 starts to extend the arm towards the object, not to reach it, but as a signal to the adult,
 318 progressively coordinating with directive gazes, vocalizations, and other behaviors to get
 319 the adult's response. This process is different from the arms-up gesture because the very
 320 first reaches of the infant do not happen in response to the caregiver's actions or within a
 321 routine. Rather, these reaching actions can become gestures because caregivers observe
 322 and respond to their infants' actions towards objects and people. In this way, the
 323 developmental pathways of different gestures are grounded in different forms of shared
 324 routines that emerge from infants' natural actions and their caregivers' responses to these
 325 actions. The following two observations illustrate the many potential meanings that early
 326 reaching gestures can take on based on the particular routines that families engage in and
 327 how adults respond.

328 At 13 months of age an infant eating a meal raised her arm while opening and
 329 closing her fingers into a fist. Her mother's response was, "Oh, you want some
 330 more?" (Carpendale & Carpendale, 2010)

331
 332 This observation shows the mother's understanding of the grasping motion as a request,
 333 based on the specific feeding context. Now, consider another observation:

334 A 2 ½ year old toddler said, "come on Grampa," reaching toward his grandfather
 335 while opening and closing his hand.

336
 337 Here, the child used the gesture in addition to words, which he had already mastered. This
 338 shows how the meanings of both the gesture and the words are rooted in the social
 339 activity in which the infant wants something, or someone, in this case. This desire is
 340 linked to a grasping action in the way described above because this is a physical
 341 manifestation of an infant's desire, to which adults can respond, and infants learn to
 342 anticipate this response. That is, they learn the meaning the action has for others.

343
 344 **From early uses of the index finger to pointing gestures.** We argue that pointing
 345 develops through this same process in which infants' desires, interests and intentions are
 346 manifest in their actions. In this case, infants tend to use their extended index finger non-
 347 communicatively at first, for example, to touch objects in exploration, or extend the index
 348 finger towards out of reach objects they wish to touch. These initially non-communicative
 349 uses become communicative as infants learn how adults respond to their actions
 350 (Carpendale & Carpendale, 2010; Carpendale et al., 2013; Kettner & Carpendale, 2018).

351 Pointing gestures can be used in many social acts. The two most well-known are
 352 imperatives and declaratives, but pointing can also be used to ask or answer a question or
 353 to inform others. From our perspective, these different uses emerge in the context of
 354 different social situations. For example, if an infant is extending her arm and index finger

355 towards a close by object such as a toy or food, the action might be interpreted by adults
356 as a request, whereas if she is pointing up at a distance to a light on the ceiling it might be
357 understood as a declarative. Other situations can be more ambiguous, and the infant's
358 action might be interpreted in either way; how caregivers choose to understand the action
359 will also depend on their prior history of shared interaction.

360 Around one year of age, infants begin to use pointing gestures in diverse ways to
361 convey different meanings. For example, to indicate a request to go in a direction a child
362 may shorten and extend his pointing hand in the direction he wants to go, or when a child
363 is pointing at something she wants to have she may also curl and uncurl her other fingers
364 in a form of a grasping action, indicating that she wants to grasp that object. Pointing may
365 also be combined with other gestures such as waving. For example, pointing to the door
366 might be combined with waving to indicate that the child wants to go out. The following
367 observation presents an example of combining gestures:

368 At 16 months, M wanted his sister in his bath, he reached toward her and then
369 pointed to the spot beside him in the bath.

370

371 These examples illustrate how pointing gestures come to be embedded in more
372 complex social situations. And infants may either make the gesture more complex by
373 adding additional movements or combine it with additional gestures to convey more
374 complex meanings.

375 Pointing with the index finger is common but not universal across cultures. For
376 example, it is considered rude and a sign of aggression to point at a person in some
377 cultures (Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1989). However, some way to direct attention would seem to be
378 important in all societies. Other body parts, such as the lips, are also used to direct others'
379 attention in some cultures (Wilkins, 2003). Although cultural practices and customs
380 influence how pointing gestures are used, we suggest that part of the developmental
381 process will be similar across cultures because of our shared embodiment and problem
382 space that human infants are born into, resulting in forms of life shared across cultures.
383 For example, human infants are born helpless and need to be carried and cared for. They
384 are interested in others and their activity, and their interests are manifest in their actions
385 such as their gaze direction, bodily orientation, and reaching actions. In turn, human
386 caregivers observe and respond to their infants' actions and interest and embed these
387 within culturally specific shared activities and routines. This provides a context for
388 human infants to develop expectations, learn what their actions mean to others, and learn
389 to communicate intentionally.

390

391 **From holding objects to showing and giving gestures.** Although less evidence
392 has been brought to light about proximal gesture development, showing and giving
393 gestures could also be considered within this family of gestures. Regarding showing
394 gestures, parents not only provide objects for their young children but tend to comment or
395 act on the objects their children are already holding or using. For example, parents often
396 name the objects that young infants are sucking on, acting on, or looking at. From these
397 repeated interactions, children progressively begin to anticipate a response from others
398 while holding and using objects (Carpendale et al., 2021). Supporting this idea,
399 McGregor and Capone (2004, see also Bates et al., 1975) have noted that children first

400 seem to extend objects they are already playing with, coordinating their actions with
 401 social gazes to the adult, before they begin to intentionally look for and extend objects
 402 towards adults to perform various social acts such as attract attention and share interest,
 403 initiate shared routines (e.g., reading a book together), make other requests (such as
 404 asking for help when using objects), or ask questions.

405 A similar process is described for the development of giving gestures (Clark,
 406 1978). Parents initially attempt to take objects that their infants are holding out or catch
 407 objects that fall from their infant's hand only to give the object back to the child while
 408 saying thank-you and smiling. In this way, parents scaffold their infant's entry into highly
 409 predictable and enjoyable give and take game-like routines (Bruner, 1983). Repeated
 410 interactions allow the infants to anticipate their parents' actions, becoming progressively
 411 more able to participate in these routines, for instance, by extending objects towards the
 412 adult and letting them fall. Soon after, infants can give and take objects by themselves
 413 and initiate these routines, gaining more understanding of the giving routines. This allows
 414 them to be part of more complex interactions where giving gestures have various social
 415 functions according to the context, such as initiating and prolonging interactions, making
 416 requests, answering questions, participating in cultural traditions (e.g., by giving objects
 417 as gifts) and even comforting others (Carpendale et al., 2021).

418

419 **2) Conventional Gestures**

420 In this category, we use the term “conventional gestures”¹ to refer to gestures
 421 rooted in cultural traditions and social practices that specify their forms, meanings, and
 422 contexts of use. In this sense, they usually have an arbitrary relation between their form
 423 and their meaning that is determined by conventions established within cultures or social
 424 groups. The age children begin to produce these gestures varies from the second half of
 425 the first year to the second year of life, depending on factors such as the specific gesture
 426 and social act performed, the child, the parents, and the culture. Broadly speaking,
 427 waving and clapping seem to be early forms of these types of gestures, at least based on
 428 studies and observations conducted in WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich,
 429 and Democratic) cultures.¹

430 If these gestures are arbitrary culturally specific actions, then it follows that they
 431 are not movements that children perform spontaneously, but that they learn through
 432 watching and interacting with others, so imitation must play some role. The question is,

¹ Conventional gestures can also be intentionally taught to children by caregivers in the context of typical everyday shared routines, such as requesting more and indicating finished. For example, *Baby Sign* is a simplified form of sign language taught to young infants (Goodwyn et al., 2000). The sign for “more,” for instance, is touching the fingers of both hands together. Although, it has been suggested that baby sign might facilitate children's language development, in a training study, it was found that this experience did not affect the children's language learning (Kirk et al., 2013; see also Nelson et al., 2012). However, through microgenetic analysis, Kirk et al. (2013) did find that “mothers in the gesture training condition were more responsive to their infants' nonverbal cues and encouraged more independent action by their infant” (p. 574, see also Vallotton, 2012). Although learning baby sign did not influence language development, it might facilitate slightly earlier communication between infants and their caregivers and thus reduce frustration on both parts. Also, Kirk et al., (2013) note that the parents in their study were already providing their children with a supportive language learning environment, but in families in which this was not the case, such support might be beneficial.

433 what role and how much can be explained through imitation. This might seem to
 434 challenge the Wittgensteinian view of meaning we are drawing on. However, we argue
 435 that even if imitation is an important element in conventional gesture development, it is
 436 neither the beginning nor the end of this process. Children do not imitate everything that

437

438 ¹ As discussed, communication depends on experience within shared routines with others. Thus, it could be
 439 argued that with a broad definition of convention as agreement, all gestures imply conventionality to some
 440 degree (see Bickhard, 2004 on situation conventions). These gestures have been referred to as “emblems”
 441 by Efron (1941), understanding them as word-like gestures whose form is related to their content only by
 442 means of conventionality. Ekman and Friesen (1969) also use the term “emblems”, emphasizing their
 443 possession of a direct verbal translation; and Kendon (1992) calls them “quotable gestures,” highlighting
 444 the idea that conventions in different social groups establish these gestures’ meaning.

445 adults do, they are selective when doing so. Hay and Murray (1982) suggest that for
 446 12month-old infants, “the modeling of a social action alone, without explicit prompts for
 447 imitation and/or a game-like pacing of modeled events, may not be sufficient to induce
 448 infants to perform that action” (p. 301). Furthermore, they argue that it should not be
 449 assumed that repeating an action is only imitation: “Infants may indeed reproduce social
 450 acts modeled by others, but their tendency to do so is selective, not automatic, and is
 451 influenced by the network of interactive events within which modeling and imitation take
 452 place” (Hay & Murray, 1982, p. 309).

453 By the time children start to perform the movements that will later become
 454 conventional gestures, they have already been immersed in previous interactions where:
 455 (1) adults use these gestures to communicate with children, making them salient for the
 456 child; (2) respond to and interpret similar non-communicative hand movements that
 457 children do in appropriate contexts; and may even (3) mold these gestures directly using
 458 the child’s hand. Furthermore, even if children reproduce the movement (and this happens
 459 with different degrees of success), it still has a long way to go before it can be considered
 460 a matured, conventional adult-like gesture. The gesture’s movement might be copied, but
 461 its social functions must be mastered through shared interactions with parental responses.
 462 In this process transitional forms of the gesture can be observed. We can illustrate this
 463 process with the development of waving gestures as follows.

464 During their first year of life, infants are typically initiated into the routine of the
 465 human custom of leave taking. Parents consistently demonstrate waving gestures (either
 466 distantly when they use them during interactions or when they use the child’s body to
 467 enact them—e.g., moving the child’s hand to say goodbye), turning them into salient and
 468 relevant behaviors for the child to reproduce. At first, infants might be motivated to learn
 469 the waving movement because of the positive responses from parents and the enjoyable
 470 shared engagement with them. This is an important social situation for their parents
 471 because ignoring a person when they are leaving is morally accountable—it would hurt
 472 someone’s feelings unless it can be accounted for in some way. Parents would like their
 473 infants to participate in the activity and acknowledge the other person as someone with
 474 value. But when infants are first introduced to waving in this context, they have little
 475 grasp of the social significance of the activity as it is too complex for them to fully
 476 understand. Many infants start attempting to imitate what their parents are doing while
 477 waving from as early as 7 to 8 months, although these early attempts may be some slight

478 movement of the arm or opening and closing of the fingers, far from the “royal wave.” In
479 a diary observation, G’s mother wrote:

480 At 7 months, G “waved” when his father left the house. It was small but
481 noticeable, a matter of opening and closing his hand after his father did it. I held
482 his arm outstretched, while waving with my other hand.

483

484 Infants first learn to imitate the physical movement, initially with varying degrees
485 of success. They gradually learn to participate in this social routine with support from
486 others. Parents may respond and interpret slight movements when they are produced at
487 specific moments. For example, in the observation of G above, his waving was identified
488 by his parents because it occurred during the leave-taking routine, on other occasions, this
489 movement might have gone unnoticed. In addition, parents also likely create the
490 appropriate context for the infant’s actions in some situations, further facilitating the
491 learning of the appropriate functions. For example, the parent might look for an object or
492 person that the infant might be waving at (as described in the following observation),
493 even when the infant’s waving movement does not begin or end at appropriate times,
494 such as leave-taking. At 11 months, G’s mother writes:

495 He is still doing erratic waving, in much the same way as he points: waving out
496 the window on the train, waving while nursing, waving from inside the carrier as I
497 walk... Waving at socially incongruous times, and virtually never or randomly at
498 socially meaningful times. He often waves out of my baby carrier - at buildings,
499 buses... Actually, I think it's kind of a mistake to say he's waving at a thing,
500 because he'll stick an arm out and wave away to himself for a whole city block.
501 And he often babbles while he does it, but not always. When he's on my back
502 other people often wave back, and if I just notice him randomly waving, I'll
503 usually say, what're you waving at? Are you waving at the ____? (filled in with
504 things he is interested in - yesterday bus and puppy, for example). Often I leave
505 our interaction at that, but sometimes I'll join in the wave as well, in his line of
506 sight, and say 'bye bye bus' or some socially appropriate thing. Yesterday I had
507 this whole interaction, up to the bus part, and then when G was still waving after
508 the bus was gone, and we did it again with a puppy.

509

510 Even when infants start to wave, they tend to generalize the gesture to a diverse
511 array of situations before, and even after, they learn to use waving in socially appropriate
512 situations. For example, MC, at 16 months, wasn’t talking yet but was able to
513 communicate with gestures and could combine two gestures such as pointing and waving.
514 Waving meant goodbye, goodnight, or going somewhere. When MC pointed to the door
515 and waved at his father (first author), this meant he wanted to go out. The following is an
516 observation of MC at 17 months:

517 He was in the bath playing with a toy that has a clear plastic part that comes off.
518 When he dropped the clear plastic part in the water it was hard to see it. When
519 this happened, he waved his hand in his "good-bye" gesture. In this situation
520 waving his hand seemed to mean that the piece was gone. The gesture is used
521 with something, or someone, is going away and in this case the toy was gone.
522 MC's hand waving can mean several different things depending on the context. It

523 can mean good-bye, good-night, or he wants to go somewhere if combined with
 524 pointing, or that something is gone, or he wants it to go. An example of the last
 525 use is that if he is finished with a book, he may wave his hand referring to the
 526 book. And then he will go and put the book away on the shelf.

527

528 In another similar observation:

529 An 18-month-old infant, J, was quite alarmed by a lobster that his grandmother
 530 showed to him, and he anxiously waved “bye bye” in an attempt to make it go
 531 away.

532

533 Savage-Rumbaugh (1986, p. 23) notes that “when the child said ‘bye-bye’ *while*
 534 *leaving*, it was a means by which the child participated in the leave-taking rituals
 535 characteristic of our species.” Then, “[l]ater, the child may use ‘bye-bye’ to precipitate the
 536 act of leaving and at this point ‘bye-bye’ advances to a spontaneous request”
 537 (SavageRumbaugh, 1986, p. 23). The following observations illustrate an infant using the
 538 waving gesture to initiate leaving taking:

539 MB (18 months) has been using opening and closing her hand as a gesture (her
 540 version of waving goodbye), not only for goodbye but also if she wants to finish
 541 anything that is going on that she wants to end. She will do this, for example, if
 542 her nanny arrives and MB wants her to leave, if her brother is doing something
 543 that she wants him to stop, or if her parents want to change her diaper. In the latter
 544 case, as well as waving, she may also try shaking her head, saying “no”, as well as
 545 vocalizing and whining.

546

547 Children initially learn to participate in the human social routine of leave-taking
 548 by moving their hand and arm. They may then start using this gesture to initiate leaving,
 549 or to comment on someone or something leaving. Soon after learning to use the gesture,
 550 they learn words to achieve the same outcome in these social situations and a similar
 551 process is observed. Words become meaningful through being based on everyday social
 552 routines.

553 In diary observations, another infant, H, at 16 months, said, “Bye bye Daddy,”
 554 while saying goodbye. And at 21 months he said “bye bye” when airplanes were
 555 going over, the dog was leaving, he or his mother turned a page on a book, and
 556 when a toy bulldozer rolled away. At 24 months, he said, “Backhoe is bye bye.
 557 Gone.” (Referring to a machine that had gone.) Here “bye bye” can mean gone.

558

559 As Savage-Rumbaugh (1986) noted, “when asked ‘Where’s Daddy?’ the child
 560 may comment ‘bye-bye’ to indicate Daddy has gone” (Savage-Rumbaugh, 1986, p. 23):
 561 “When a child says ‘bye-bye’ to indicate that someone who was in the room has now
 562 departed, the word becomes divorced from the child’s own immediate action in a most
 563 significant way” (Savage-Rumbaugh, 1986, p. 23).

564

565 It is interesting to note that, rather than using waving more narrowly when
 566 compared to the adult use, infants generalize this movement to a large number of
 situations, resulting in the waving gesture having many different communicative

567 functions. These early extended social uses have also been documented with other
 568 conventional gestures. For example, clapping gestures are initially used by parents as a
 569 means to express joy and acknowledge accomplishments, beginning during the first year
 570 of their infants' life (e.g., children learn to clap during games with songs). Through
 571 participating in shared interactions of celebration, children gradually learn to use clapping
 572 when an activity is finished. Only later will they selectively use clapping to positively
 573 evaluate the outcome of an action (just as parents begin to selectively clap for them only
 574 when the child's action is successful). However, in this process other uses can arise. A
 575 parent reported that at 14 to 15 months her infant, O, used clapping gestures combined
 576 with reaching and pointing to request actions or objects, or to request an action that was
 577 difficult for her, such as to have her water bottle opened. She would give her water bottle
 578 to her mother and then clap, which meant that she wanted her bottle opened. In a video
 579 recording, she initially uses two claps for the request but in a second request she
 580 abbreviates it to one clap. Presumably, she had learned that her parents used this gesture
 581 when she had accomplished something difficult, so she appeared to use it to initiate her
 582 mother doing something difficult such as opening her water bottle or reaching an object
 583 that was beyond her reach.

584 The observations above illustrate how gestures such as waving develop through a
 585 gradual, complex process with parental scaffolding that involves transitional phases
 586 consisting of learning the movement, as well as learning the uses of this action as a
 587 gesture within the appropriate social routines. These observations illustrate a process that
 588 is consistent with the action-based, process-relational view.

589

590 **3) Symbolic Gestures**

591 The third form of gesture we consider has various labels, but perhaps they are
 592 most commonly known as symbolic gestures (Bates et al., 1979; Fasolo & D'Odorico,
 593 2012). These gestures are also referred to as "characterizing signs" (Goldin-Meadow &
 594 Feldman, 1977), "enactive gestures" (Zinober & Martlew, 1985), or "iconic gestures"
 595 (Özçaliskan & Goldin-Meadow, 2009; Wermelinger et al., 2020) and used to specify
 596 actions or objects through similarities between their form and some attribute of the
 597 referent. For example, in one observation a child points at a jar and then makes a twisting
 598 motion to comment on their mother opening it (Goldin-Meadow & Feldman, 1977).
 599 Symbolic gestures seem to be mostly used during the second year of life (around 15 to 18
 600 months of age), coinciding with the appearance of the first words. Research reports some
 601 contradictory findings in their developmental pathway. Although some authors describe a
 602 decrease in their frequency when language becomes prominent in the child's
 603 communicative repertoire (Iverson et al., 1994), others report relative stability with a
 604 remarkable increase around 30 months of age (Murillo & Casla, 2020; Özçaliskan &
 605 Goldin-Meadow, 2011). However, children and adults still use this form of
 606 communication to complement language or if the situation does not make language
 607 possible, due to, for example, noise or distance (Acredolo & Goodwyn, 1985, 1988).
 608 Acredolo and Goodwyn (1985, 1988) studied the developmental pathway of symbolic
 609 gestures in children between 12 and 20 months old. They conclude that symbolic gestures
 610 are frequently used by children at these ages to refer to, for example, flowers, dogs, and
 611 horses, and to make requests such as to go out. These gestures seem to involve two

612 apparently different processes of acquisition. The first one was the most common. It
613 involved gestures that were directly taught by the child's parents, whether it was
614 intentionally or unintentionally. Children learned these symbolic gestures in the context
615 of frequently repeated routines initiated by their parents, such as sniffing to represent
616 flowers. In these cases, the form of the gesture came from the parents, similar to the
617 process described above for conventional gesture acquisition. The second process
618 described by the authors had some spontaneous component. These gestures seemed to be
619 the children's own inventions based on their previous and repeated experiences with the
620 represented objects and their specific contexts of use. For example, based on the routine
621 of bouncing in her caregiver's legs, a child bounced her torso to indicate a horse in
622 different contexts; or a child performed the action of turning her hand like turning a
623 doorknob to refer to going out, based on a leave-taking routine. In addition, the authors
624 note that these early symbolic gestures, whether they were taught or idiosyncratic, seem
625 to be based on the use of the objects (in actions) rather than their perceptive properties.
626 For example, children frequently pantomimed bouncing a ball to refer to a ball instead
627 indicating a round shape.

628 Due to the way these gestures develop in shared social routines within families
629 they can be specific to families and thus are idiosyncratic. However, similarities can also
630 be found that are likely due to cultural and interactional commonalities. For example,
631 panting can function to refer to a dog and sniffing to refer to a flower.

632 From parental diaries the following are observations of symbolic gesturing.

633

634 At 19 months MC used a fluid movement of his arm tracing a wave in the water
635 that meant swimming.

636

637 GC, at 18 months, was very tidy and he had a gesture that meant they should
638 clean this up. It seemed to have been inspired by the hand motion of holding a
639 sponge and cleaning. That is, he extended his arm and opened his hand and used a
640 rotating motion of his hand. When they are in the elevator or lobby and it was wet
641 or muddy, he seemed to be indicating to his mother that they should clean it up.
642 She could recognize the meaning of these gesture by their previous history of
643 interactions.

644

645 Some transitional forms of symbolic gestures can also be observed, as children
646 enact properties of objects, actions, or events, and it is the adult's interpretation of these
647 behaviors as meaningful (based on previous interactions with the child) that results in the
648 development of the gesture. Here is an example of a diary observation:

649

650 In the middle of her second year, D loved music and often responded to the sound
651 of music by dancing, usually starting with her arms raised, elbows out, and
652 swinging vigorously. She also knew that music played from both the CD player
653 and the computer. At 17 months D walked up to the computer and moved her
654 arms as if she was dancing, and looked at the computer and then at her mother,
655 who asked her, do you want music? And D said "Yes". After that, she often
656 repeated the same movement (which had become a gesture for the child and the

657 parents), standing either in front of the computer or in front of the CD player
 658 when she wanted her parents to turn on music.

659

660 These examples of this form of gesture occur with infants from 16 to 19 months.
 661 With adults and older children who do understand the potential to communicate with
 662 something like pantomime, they could be aware of intentionally selecting an action that
 663 would be understandable to others. This might be the case in some of the examples in
 664 Goldin-Meadow and Feldman's work (1977). There are also games that children and
 665 adults play in which a meaning must be conveyed with only the use of gestures. In this
 666 case, many of these gestures may be intentionally invented and are likely based on
 667 actions the adults have enough experience with so that they can expect to be understood.

668 Some authors consider that, in contrast to indexical gestures (e.g., pointing) in
 669 which the social function cannot be evoked from its morphology but from its referents
 670 and the context of the interaction, symbols are content-loaded gestures that "carry their
 671 meaning in their form" (Murillo & Casla, 2020, p. 105) and are relatively
 672 contextindependent (Iverson et al., 1994). This idea may lead us to think of symbolic
 673 gestures as tags for referents, just as in the naming view of language described previously
 674 (see section 1.2.). However, from a Wittgensteinian perspective, meaning cannot be fixed
 675 to symbolic gestures. Instead, just like the other gestural forms described above, symbolic
 676 gestures acquire meaning through interaction within shared social activities. Rather than
 677 the form carrying meaning, the form evokes the routine in which the meaning is based,
 678 therefore the form can be used to communicate because of the shared understanding of
 679 the routine.

680

681 **Discussion**

682 We have described three families of gestures with somewhat different
 683 developmental pathways, but we have also suggested that there is a common process on
 684 which all these gestures are based. That is, communication is based on shared social
 685 routines, therefore infants learn to communicate through being immersed in these shared
 686 routines, in which they act and interact with others and gradually develop an
 687 understanding of the meaning that their actions have for others. It is through interactions
 688 with others, within various types of routines, that infants' actions can become gestures.
 689 We have reviewed arguments that meaning is not fixed to gestures or utterances but
 690 instead is based on shared practices and social routines. Shared routines vary based on
 691 whether they are primarily initiated by the infant or the caregiver. Some gestures
 692 originate in routines that follow caregivers' responses to infants' actions (e.g., the
 693 development of request gestures). For conventional gestures, routines are present within
 694 the culture and infants are initiated into the social routine and the associated actions, such
 695 as waving. From the relational perspective we take gestures emerge from action and
 696 interaction and thus we expect transitional forms of gestures depending on the
 697 developmental processes involved, which we discuss below.

698 In the first category, infants' actions such as reaching or touching are intentional
 699 and goal directed for the child and are therefore meaningful for the parent because they
 700 indicate and make manifest to the parent the child's desire and interest. The meaning is
 701 already embedded in the interactive routine, which is initiated by the child's spontaneous

702 actions. However, the infant is not yet aware that she is communicating. Through the
703 parent's responses to the infant's actions, the child learns to anticipate these responses,
704 and learns the meaning that her actions have for caregivers. The infant then gradually
705 learns to intend to communicate. In this case transitional forms would involve infants'
706 emerging awareness that they are communicating. We suggest that these forms of gestures
707 may be similar across cultures because typical human infants' embodiment mean that
708 they usually learn to grasp with their hands, and that in the problem space they encounter
709 there may be some objects that are out of reach for them. In this category, the child plays
710 an important role in initiating these routines, assuming that the caregivers respond to the
711 infant's actions and he or she can then learn to anticipate these responses (e.g., Canfield,
712 1999).

713 In the case of conventional gestures, caregivers play a role in initiating the child
714 into a cultural activity pattern, such as waving in the context of leave-taking. The infant
715 initially learns the hand movement through imitation, or through the parent directly
716 moving the infant's arm and hand. In this case transitional forms of understanding can be
717 seen as infants gradually learning the appropriate social context for the use of a gesture to
718 be meaningful. An example of transitional forms in the development of conventional
719 gestures is illustrated by our discussion of infants using waving in many different
720 contexts, some of which are inappropriate, before learning to use the waving movement
721 in appropriate contexts. We also discussed examples of how children may move from
722 participating in appropriate social contexts through gestures (e.g., waving back when the
723 parent is leaving), to attempting to initiate the routines (e.g., waving to indicate that the
724 child wants to leave). A child may move beyond using the newly learned actions only
725 within the appropriate context, and, as shown in the observations we presented,
726 overgeneralize these movements to mean "gone" (e.g., after an object disappears), "want
727 it to be gone", "finished" (e.g., waving at the book), and so on. However, it is only
728 possible for infants to learn the appropriate uses through caregivers interpreting,
729 responding to, and embedding the infant's actions within the appropriate routines, based
730 on socially appropriate uses. We argue that this is a common thread in the development of
731 different types of gestures.

732 Although some conventional gestures may be culturally specific, social acts like
733 leave taking may be a typical part of human forms of life across cultures, but
734 accomplished with different gestures. The practice of recognizing leave taking may be
735 common across cultures because it acknowledges the value of persons, although how it is
736 accomplished, and its relative importance, could vary. Acknowledging others as persons
737 is involved in many other social acts such as greetings, which also may be an important
738 part of human interaction, although how this is accomplished can vary across groups.
739 In the third case of symbolic gesturing the meaning is based on the gesture drawing
740 something from the object or action so an observer can understand the intention. There
741 are various possible developmental pathways. At the age of the children in the examples
742 we have given, there might be two possible developmental pathways to explore. One
743 possible pathway might involve the caregiver playing a role in intentionally or
744 unintentionally introducing the shared social routine in which the gesture functions and so
745 this would be similar to conventional gestures. In the case of G's cleaning action, D's
746 dancing motion, and M's swimming movement, a second pathway seems to emerge. It

747 could be that in recalling these activities they embodied their thought with the action, and
748 caregivers, seeing this, might respond. This way of setting up this social routine would be
749 somewhat similar to the first category of gestures that emerge based on the child's
750 spontaneous actions. Since it seems that symbolic gestures may develop through either of
751 the two processes discussed in the first two families, it follows that the transitional forms
752 expected might be similar to those discussed for those forms.

753 We are not proposing that these categories are hard and fast boundaries, but
754 instead we think that they form a system with which to organize diverse forms of gestures
755 in order to understand the similarities and differences in the developmental processes
756 involved. For example, pointing may be initially based on a spontaneous action that is
757 responded to, but if this gesture is considered rude in some cultures it may be discouraged
758 and other forms of indicating, such as lip pointing, may be encouraged, which may be
759 considered conventional. There could be debate regarding whether head nodding for yes
760 and head shaking for no are conventional or natural gestures. Darwin (1872/1998) and
761 Spitz (1957) argued that head shaking is based on infants' natural reactions to refuse an
762 offer of food by turning their head to the side (see Kettner & Carpendale, 2013).
763 However, these might be conventional gestures because although they are widespread
764 across cultures, some cultures use them differently. There could be an initial natural
765 reaction of the infant turning her head away, but performing the social act of indicating
766 "No," either with a gesture or a word, can vary in complexity. Refusal of food can be a
767 simpler act than indicating no in response to a question (Kettner & Carpendale, 2013).
768 Although we have not discussed individual differences in communicative development,
769 we acknowledge their importance from a relational perspective. Individual differences
770 tend to be neglected in this area of research with a few exceptions, such as Acredolo and
771 Goodwyn's (1988) discussion of the striking individual differences they found in the use
772 of symbolic gestures. In both a cross-sectional and a longitudinal study Acredolo and
773 Goodwyn (1988) reported individual differences and a gender difference with girls
774 showing a stronger tendency to use symbolic gesturing, which was especially strong in
775 first born girls. Temperament is one way to assess individual differences in infancy. For
776 example, infants reported by their parents to be higher in their ability to orient and to
777 regulate their emotions, as indicated by their ability to be soothed, as well as being higher
778 in positive emotions, were also reported to use more communicative gestures (Ollas et al.,
779 2020). The authors suggest that these temperament characteristics might be important in
780 facilitating increasingly positive social interactions, and, consistent with our relational
781 perspective, this experience in interaction with their caregivers may in turn result in
782 advances in communication.

783

784 **Conclusion**

785 Our goal has been to draw attention to various forms of gestures that we have
786 grouped into three types in terms of their developmental origins—their genealogy. Most
787 research attention has been devoted to pointing gestures, but we have discussed some of
788 the many other gestures that infants use during their first years. Although these diverse
789 gestures might appear to be acquired in very different ways, one theme in this article is to
790 point out how such gestures are learned in the context of shared social routines. What
791 may differ is the relative role of the caregiver and child in initiating the routine, and

792 whether this role is initially intentional or unintentional. That is, although somewhat
793 different processes may be involved in these different forms of gestures, they are still
794 based on the same process through which meaning is conveyed—being based on shared
795 experiences within social routines, as described by Mead (1934) and Wittgenstein
796 (1953/2009). Thus, we have illustrated the importance of basing our investigations on an
797 adequate conception of meaning in order to recognize the similarity in the underlying
798 processes involved in early communicative development.

799

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801 This research has been reviewed and approved by the Simon Fraser University Research
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803 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

804 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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813 **Author Contributions**

814 The first author wrote the first draft. The second and third authors added paragraphs and
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